

Republic of Serbia
MINISTRY OF SCIENCE,
TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

REPUBLIC OF SERBIA
AUTONOMOUS PROVINCE OF VOJVODINA
PROVINCIAL SECRETARIAT FOR HIGHER EDUCATION
AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

DEPARTMENT OF
ENVIRONMENTAL
ENGINEERING AND
OCCUPATIONAL
SAFETY AND HEALTH

4th INTERNATIONAL STUDENT CONFERENCE

DISC2024

**Faculty of Technical Sciences
University of Novi Sad**

**Hybrid event
5th & 6th December, 2024
Novi Sad, Serbia**

Organizers:

Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

The 4th International Student Conference - DISC2024 is supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Republic of Serbia and the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research AP Vojvodina.

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

502(048.3)
331.45/.46(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Student Conference – DISC2024 (4 ; 2024 ; Novi Sad)

Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / 4th International Student Conference – DISC2024, hybrid event, 5-6th December 2024, Novi Sad ; [editors Maja Petrović, Ivana Mihajlović, Nevena Živančev]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Technical Sciences, 2024

Način pristupa (URL):

https://www.izzs.uns.ac.rs/uploads/files/shares/Abstract_Book_DISC2024.pdf. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 24.2.2025. - Nasl. s naslovnog ekrana.

ISBN 978-86-6022-715-9

а) Заштита животне средине -- Апстракти б) Заштита на раду -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 163666185

Scientific and Program Committee:

Dr. Dejan Ubavin, President, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dr. Dragana Tomašević Pilipović, Vice-president, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

- Dr. Ivan Špánik, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia
Dr. Friedo Zölzer, University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Czech Republic
Dr. Killi Uday Kumar, University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Czech Republic
Dr. Juraj Ševčík, Palacký University Olomouc, Czech Republic
Dr. João Paulo Teixeira, University of Porto, Portugal
Dr. António Canatário Duarte, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Portugal
Dr. Stevo Lavrnić, University of Bologna, Italy
Dr. Jakub Drewnowski, Gdańsk University of Technology, Poland
Dr. Zakhar Maletskyi, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway
Dr. Agnieszka Cuprys, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway
Dr. Mira Čelić, Catalan Institute for Water Research, Spain
Dr. Arijana Filipić, National Institute of Biology, Slovenia
Dr. Viktoria Blanka-Vegi, University of Szeged, Hungary
Dr. Patrick Ssebugere, Makerere University, Uganda
Dr. Christine Kyarimpa, Kyambogo University, Uganda
Dr. Solomon Omwoma Lugas, Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology, Kenya
Dr. Elizabeth Ndunda, Machakos University, Kenya
Dr. Eliezer Brown Mwakalapa, Mbeya University of Science and Technology, Tanzania
Dr. Fikira Kimbokota, Mkwawa University College of Education, Tanzania
Dr. Ali Hgeig, Nalut University, Libya
Dr. Bojan Jovanovski, University of Applied Sciences, Austria
Dr. Trajče Velkovski, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Dr. Jasmina Chaloska, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Dr. Radmil Polenakovikj, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
- Dr. Ivona Nuić, University of Split, Croatia
Dr. Aleksandra Anić Vučinić, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Dr. Emina Hadžić, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Merima Šahinagić-Isović, Dzemal Bijedic University of Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Nedim Čelebić, Sarajevo School of Science and Technology, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Biljana Šćepanović, University of Montenegro, Montenegro
Dr. Aleksandra Petrović, University of Kragujevac, Serbia
Dr. Aleksandra Tubić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Đurđa Kerkez, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Bogdana Vujić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Maja Milanović, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Igor Peško, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Vladimir Mučenski, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Andrea Ivanišević, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Jelena Čulibrk, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Minja Bolesnikov, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Danijela Ćirić Lalić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Ivana Mihajlović, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Bojan Batinić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Srđan Kovačević, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Zoran Čepić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Organizing Committee:

Dr. Maja Petrović, President, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dr. Nevena Živančev, Vice-president, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

- Dr. Maja Sremački, InoSens d.o.o., Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Bojana Zoraja, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Jovana Topalić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Miljan Šunjević, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
MSc. Jelena Mirjanić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
MSc. Jovana Krtinić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- MSc. Dunja Istrat, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
MSc. Jasmina Naerac, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
MSc. Tijana Adamov, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

LEAD EXPOSURE AND LUNG CANCER: PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF SCREENING ANALYSIS IN FEMALE

Ševo M.^{1,2}, Sazdanić Velikić D.^{1,3}, Milanović M.¹, Milošević N.¹, Milić N.¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia
(e-mail: 902012d23@mf.uns.ac.rs)

²IMC Banja Luka-Center of Radiotherapy, Part of Affidea Group, Dvanaest beba, 78000 Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

³Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for Pulmonary Oncology, Put doktora Goldmana 4, 21204 Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Abstract:

The increasing anthropogenic activities has led to both environmental and occupational exposure to heavy metals. Most of them are identified as global health treat due to the increasing vulnerability to adverse health outcomes associated with their occurrence in water, soil, food and even air. Moreover, exposure to heavy metals might be linked with the increased risk of cancer onset and progression. The screening for elevated heavy metals in urine samples is a method of choice for assessing environmental risk factors in lung cancer. In this study, 25 female patients (older than 18) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of adenocarcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia, were enrolled. The presence of lead (Pb) in morning spot urine samples was evaluated by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) method. Based on the obtained results, in 28% (7/25) urine samples lead was above the limit of detection (4 µg/L). Pb levels were above 12 µg/L in 20% (5/25) of women patients. The highest Pb urinary concentration was 19.34 µg/L. Lead and its inorganic compounds are classified as possibly carcinogenic to humans- class 2B. According to the available literature data, the elevated Pb concentrations in blood are found in patients with breast and bladder cancer. Among others, Pb have been also identified as non-cancer health risk metal. Apart from mining, manufacturing and recycling activities, different everyday products including traditional home remedies, cosmetics and jewelry might be possible Pb sources. Pb tendency to bioaccumulate was confirmed in Vojvodina i.e. Pb permitted levels were exceeded for potato and carrots which are commonly used in diet in this region. Biomonitoring studies that will include large number of lung cancer patients are needed in order to elucidate the relationship between exposure to lead and the initialization and development of lung cancer.

Keywords: *pollution; heavy metals; risk factors; biomonitoring; ICP-MS*

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia [Grant number 003076431 2024 09418 003 000 000 001].